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Play-Based Learning Strategies And Nursery Pupils' School Attendance In Rivers State, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

This study examined the relationship between play-based learning strategies and nursery pupils' school attendance in Rivers State, Nigeria. Guided by three research questions and three null hypotheses, the study adopted a correlational research design. The population comprised 8,765 teachers from 2,113 accredited private secondary schools, with a stratified random sample of 383 teachers, drawn from the population using Taro Yamane. Data were collected using validated 4-point rating scale questionnaires, titled: Play-Based Learning Strategies Scale (PBLSS) and Nursery Pupils' School Attendance Scale (NPSAS), which were validated, and reliability coefficients of 0.83 and 0.79 were obtained using Cronbach's Alpha. Pearson Product-Moment Correlation Coefficient (PPMC) was used to answer the research questions and test the hypotheses at the 0.05 level of significance. Findings revealed a very and significant relationship between a very strong relationship between free play, guided play, structured play and nursery pupils' school attendance in Rivers State. Based on these findings, it was concluded that effective integration of play-based learning in nursery education is crucial for enhancing pupils' regular school attendance and sustaining early childhood engagement. Hence, it is recommended that nursery school proprietors and teachers in Rivers State should continue to integrate daily free play periods into the curriculum to create enjoyable learning environments that motivate pupils to attend school regularly.

Keywords: Play-Based, Learning Strategies, Nursery Pupils, School Attendance

INTRODUCTION

Education is a fundamental human right and a major catalyst for national development. Quality education equips individuals with the knowledge, skills and attitudes necessary to participate meaningfully in socio-economic life and contributes to broader sustainable development goals (UNICEF, 2025). Within the global education framework, Early Childhood Care and Education (ECCE) is recognised as a crucial phase that lays the foundation for lifelong learning, cognitive growth and social adjustment (UNESCO, 2025). ECCE covers the critical period from birth to around eight years, during which the foundations for language, numeracy, social skills and emotional regulation are established (UNESCO, 2025). Neuroscience research underscores this window as one of rapid brain development, where enriching experiences can yield lasting cognitive and behavioural benefits (UNESCO, 2025). However, despite global progress, many countries, particularly low- and middle-income nations, continue to face

considerable challenges in expanding access to quality early education and ensuring consistent school participation among young learners (UNICEF, 2025).

In Nigeria, the education system formally incorporates early childhood education as the preparatory stage before primary schooling, reflecting recognition of its importance in bridging home learning environments and formal education settings (UNESCO, 2023). This sub-sector aims to enhance school readiness, improve developmental outcomes, and reduce inequities that disadvantage marginalised children (UNESCO, 2023). Despite policy frameworks and targeted interventions, data show significant gaps in enrolment and regular attendance across the age range that encompasses early childhood and primary education in Nigeria. Currently, only a small proportion of children aged 36–59 months participate in organised early learning programmes, and primary attendance rates remain below universal targets, with marked regional disparities (UNICEF, 2025). Such inconsistencies in attendance compromise instructional continuity and weaken the cumulative developmental processes that enable success in later grades.

Pupils' school attendance is a complex and multi-dimensional construct influenced by socio-economic status, parental expectations, school quality, and classroom practices. Regular attendance is critical because it ensures continuity of instruction and social engagement, which are correlated with positive academic achievement and reduced dropout likelihood (UNICEF, 2025). Inconsistent attendance patterns, especially during the transition from early childhood to primary schooling, can disrupt learning progression and weaken foundational skill acquisition. Though Nigeria's official policy prescribes free and compulsory primary education, attendance remains variable; many children either enrol late, attend irregularly, or drop out early, particularly in contexts where schools are perceived as unengaging or punitive (UNICEF, 2025). Nursery pupils' school attendance is commonly defined as the regular presence of pupils at school and in scheduled classes, measured not only by days present but also by indicators such as punctuality, authorised and unauthorised absences, partial-day attendance, and chronic absenteeism (for example, missing 10% or more of school days in a year). These indicators together signal the degree of a pupil's participation and engagement with schooling and are used by education systems to monitor access and retention, which are made possible in many instances through play-based learning strategies (UNESCO Institute for Statistics; Kearney, 2022; Healthy Children, 2024).

Play-based learning strategies are widely defined as pedagogical approaches that use play as a central medium through which children actively construct knowledge, skills and understanding. UNICEF and the LEGO Foundation (2018) define play-based learning as learning experiences that are joyful, meaningful, actively engaging, iterative and socially interactive, enabling children to explore concepts in developmentally appropriate ways. Similarly, Hirsh-Pasek et al. (2020) conceptualise play-based learning as a continuum of child-initiated and adult-guided activities that intentionally align playful experiences with curriculum goals to support cognitive, social, and emotional development. These strategies take several forms, including free play, guided play, and structured play (Parker et al., 2022). Other recognised types include cooperative play, imaginative or pretend play, and game-based learning, all of which foster motivation, creativity and active participation while supporting curriculum attainment when effectively integrated into classroom practice. However, this study focused on free play, guided play, and structured play.

Free play in early childhood education is commonly defined as child-initiated, voluntary, and intrinsically motivated activity that is freely chosen by children and not directed by adults, allowing them autonomy over what, how, and with whom they play (Pyle & Danniels, 2017; Wood, 2014). Through free play, children explore their interests, regulate their emotions, and develop social competence in a low-pressure learning environment, which can make school experiences enjoyable and meaningful. This enjoyment has been shown to promote pupils' school attendance, as children are more willing to attend school when they associate it with freedom, enjoyment, and positive peer interaction rather than rigid academic demands (Bodrova & Leong, 2019). According to Zosh et al. (2018), Cheruiyot (2024) and Obijiofor et al. (2024) free play predicts or determines pupils' school attendance when play is well-supported and integrated into the school routine, fostering a sense of belonging and emotional security that encourages regular

participation. However, when free play is poorly structured or undervalued, it leads to concerns from parents and educators that excessive play reduces academic focus, which may discourage attendance or predict low attendance in contexts where schooling is viewed primarily through an academic lens (Fisher et al., 2013, UNESCO, 2023). Thus, while free play can significantly enhance pupils' motivation to attend school, its impact on attendance depends largely on how it is balanced with guided learning and communicated as a valuable educational practice.

Guided play in early childhood education is defined as a playful learning approach in which children retain control over their activities, while adults intentionally scaffold the environment, pose open-ended questions, or subtly guide interactions towards specific learning goals (Weisberg, Hirsh-Pasek, & Golinkoff, 2016; Toub et al., 2018). Unlike free play, guided play balances child autonomy with purposeful adult involvement, ensuring that learning objectives are embedded within enjoyable play experiences. This approach can promote pupils' school attendance by making school both engaging and meaningful, as children are more motivated to attend when learning feels playful, supportive, and responsive to their interests rather than overly didactic (Hassinger-Das et al., 2020). A positive relationship, therefore, exists between guided play and pupils' school attendance, as the structured support provided by teachers enhances children's confidence, curiosity, and sense of achievement, all of which encourage regular school participation (Allee-Herndon, Roberts, & Stevenson, 2019). However, a negative impact may arise when guided play becomes overly teacher-directed, reducing children's sense of choice and turning play into disguised instruction, which can diminish enjoyment and weaken motivation to attend school (Pyle, DeLuca, & Danniels, 2017; Nicolopoulou, 2018). Consequently, guided play has the potential to positively influence pupils' school attendance when adult guidance is sensitive and developmentally appropriate, but its benefits may be undermined if play loses its voluntary and enjoyable nature.

Structured play in early childhood education is defined as play activities that are intentionally planned, organised, and guided by adults, with clear rules, learning objectives, and expected outcomes, while still retaining playful elements that engage young learners (Moyles, 2015; Saracho, 2012). In structured play, teachers select materials, set boundaries, and guide interactions to support the development of cognitive, social, and behavioural skills aligned with curricular goals. This form of play can promote pupils' school attendance by providing predictable routines, clear expectations, and a sense of competence, which help children feel secure and successful within the school environment, thereby increasing their willingness to attend regularly (Bergen, 2014; Ramani & Brownell, 2014). A strong link therefore exists between structured play and pupils' school attendance when activities are developmentally appropriate and engaging, as they foster discipline, cooperation, and positive teacher-pupil relationships that enhance school attachment (Hedges & Cooper, 2018). However, when structured play is excessively rigid or overly academic, it may limit children's autonomy and enjoyment, leading to reduced motivation and, indirectly, poorer attendance outcomes (Pellegrini, 2009). In contrast, free play maintains a complementary relationship with attendance: it can positively influence attendance by offering enjoyment and emotional release, yet may have a negative impact where it dominates the school day without structure, raising concerns about academic value and consistency (Moyles, 2010). Thus, the influence of structured play on pupils' school attendance is most effective when it is balanced with opportunities for free play, ensuring both engagement and educational purpose.

Consequently, within this broader educational landscape, play-based learning strategies play a pivotal role. In short, when classrooms are organised around play that connects to curriculum goals, pupils are more likely to attend regularly (fewer unauthorised absences and less chronic absenteeism) because school becomes a place they want to be and where their learning needs are met. However, quality is uneven in practice; many early learning settings in Nigeria lack adequate infrastructure, instructional materials and trained personnel to implement developmentally appropriate pedagogy (UNESCO, 2023). Without supportive and stimulating classroom environments, young learners may experience school as dull or disconnected from their interests, which can reduce motivation and attendance once they enter formal schooling. Given these challenges, attention has turned to pedagogical strategies that can improve

young learners' engagement and attendance. Play-based learning is one such approach that has gained traction internationally and within parts of Nigeria as a developmentally aligned pedagogy for early childhood settings. Play-based learning emphasises child-initiated and guided play activities that are structured to support exploration, problem-solving and social interaction within meaningful contexts. This approach aligns with constructivist theories that posit children learn best through active engagement and social participation in authentic tasks (Cheruiyot, 2024). Empirical research shows that play-based methods can enhance early literacy, socio-emotional development and overall engagement in early learners (Cheruiyot, 2024; Obijiofor *et al.*, 2024). For example, studies in Southeastern Nigeria found significant positive correlations between play-based activities and social skills development in nursery children, suggesting these strategies foster cooperation, sharing and empathy, skills that underpin classroom engagement (Obijiofor *et al.*, 2024).

Despite these promising findings, the relationship between play-based learning and school attendance has not been extensively studied in the Nigerian context, particularly at the state level. While improved engagement may plausibly encourage children to attend school more regularly, limited research has empirically tested this association. Moreover, implementation challenges such as inadequate play materials, insufficient teacher training and unclear policy guidance often hinder effective play-based practice in early childhood settings (Cheruiyot, 2024). Understanding whether and how play-based learning strategies correlate with attendance in Rivers State is therefore crucial. Rivers State, despite relatively higher education participation rates compared with some other regions, still grapples with issues of classroom quality and attendance consistency across urban and rural communities.

This study addresses these empirical gaps by investigating the correlational relationship between play-based learning strategies and nursery pupils' school attendance in Rivers State. By situating the research within the broader educational and developmental context of early childhood, the study aims to provide evidence that can inform teachers, school leaders and policymakers about pedagogical practices that not only promote holistic learning but also encourage consistent school participation. If play-based strategies are found to be positively associated with attendance, this could justify integrating play-oriented approaches more fully into early childhood and early primary curricula and teacher professional development programmes in Rivers State and beyond.

Statement of the Problem

Early childhood education is very important because it helps children develop basic skills and a positive attitude towards learning. However, many nursery schools, which capture the early child education system in Rivers State, still face problems with pupils' school attendance. Some children come late, miss school often, or do not attend regularly. This situation may be caused by low interest in school activities, parents' views about schooling, and the quality of learning experiences provided in schools. A major concern is whether teaching methods used in nursery schools are interesting, suitable for young children, and able to encourage them to attend school regularly.

Play-based learning is known to be an effective way of teaching young children because it allows them to learn through play, interaction, and enjoyment. However, in many nursery schools in Rivers State, play-based learning is not always properly used. Some schools rely mostly on teacher-centred and rigid classroom activities, which may limit children's participation. Even where play is included, little attention is given to different types of play, such as free play, guided play, and structured play, and how each affects pupils' interest and attendance. As a result, children may lose interest in school and attend less regularly. In addition, there is limited research in Rivers State that clearly shows how specific play-based learning strategies affect pupils' school attendance at the nursery level. This lack of information makes it difficult for teachers, school managers, and policymakers to choose the best play strategies to improve attendance. Therefore, this study seeks to examine the relationship between free play, guided play, structured play, and pupils' school attendance in nursery schools in Rivers State.

Aim and Objectives of the Study.

This study aimed to investigate the relationship between play-based learning strategies and nursery pupils' school attendance in Rivers State. Specifically, the study sought to:

1. examine the relationship between free play and nursery pupils' school attendance in Rivers State.
2. determine the relationship between guided play and nursery pupils' school attendance in Rivers State.
3. find out the relationship between structured play and nursery pupils' school attendance in Rivers State.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study.

1. What is the relationship between free play and nursery pupils' school attendance in Rivers State?
2. What is the relationship between guided play and nursery pupils' school attendance in Rivers State?
3. What is the relationship between structured play and nursery pupils' school attendance in Rivers State?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were tested at a 0.05 level of significance.

1. There is no significant relationship between free play and nursery pupils' school attendance in Rivers State.
2. There is no significant relationship between guided play and nursery pupils' school attendance in Rivers State.
3. There is no significant relationship between structured play and nursery pupils' school attendance in Rivers State.

METHODOLOGY

This study adopted a correlational research design to examine the relationship between the independent and dependent variables. The population comprised 8,765 teachers (2,062 males and 6,703 females) drawn from 2,113 accredited private nursery schools in Rivers State. A sample of 383 teachers was determined using the Taro Yamane formula and selected through a stratified random sampling technique. Data were collected using a structured questionnaire consisting of two scales: the Play-Based Learning Strategies Scale (PBLSS) and the Nursery Pupils' School Attendance Scale (NPSAS). The instrument was divided into two sections: Section A elicited demographic information, while Section B addressed research questions one to three. Responses were rated on a 4-point Likert scale of Strongly Agree, Agree, Disagree, and Strongly Disagree. The instrument was validated, and reliability testing using Cronbach's Alpha yielded coefficients of 0.83 for PBLSS and 0.79 for NPSAS. With the support of three research assistants, the researcher administered 383 copies of the questionnaire, of which 369 (96%) were returned, and 364 (95%) were found valid for analysis. Pearson Product-Moment Correlation Coefficient (PPMC) was used to answer the research questions and test the hypotheses at the 0.05 level of significance. Correlation values were interpreted as Very Strong (0.90–1.00), Strong (0.70–0.80), Moderate (0.50–0.60), Weak (0.30–0.40), and Very Weak (below 0.20).

RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

The results of the analysed data for the research questions and their corresponding hypotheses are presented in tables as shown below.

Research Question 1: *What is the relationship between free play and nursery pupils’ school attendance in Rivers State?*

Table 1: Pearson Product-Moment Correlation (PPMC) showing the Relationship between Free Play and Nursery Pupils’ School Attendance in Rivers State

Variables	n	df	r	Decision
Free Play	364			
		362	0.872	Very Strong Relationship
Nursery Pupils’ School Attendance	364			

Decision Rule: 0.00 – 0.19 = Very Weak, 0.20 – 0.39 = Weak, 0.40 – 0.59 = Moderate, 0.60 – 0.79 = Strong, 0.80 – 1.00 Very Strong

To address Research Question 1, the result in Table 1 shows a Pearson correlation coefficient ($r = 0.872$), indicating a very strong positive linear relationship between free play and nursery pupils’ school attendance in Rivers State. This coefficient suggests that approximately 87% of the maximum possible positive relationship exists between the two variables, reflecting a very strong positive relationship. Hence, there is a very strong relationship between free play and nursery pupils’ school attendance in Rivers State.

Research Question 2: *What is the relationship between guided play and nursery pupils’ school attendance in Rivers State?*

Table 2: Pearson Product-Moment Correlation (PPMC) showing the Relationship between Guided Play and Nursery Pupils’ School Attendance in Rivers State

Variables	n	df	r	Decision
Guided Play	364			
		362	0.803	Very Strong Relationship
Nursery Pupils’ School Attendance	364			

Decision Rule: 0.00 – 0.19 = Very Weak, 0.20 – 0.39 = Weak, 0.40 – 0.59 = Moderate, 0.60 – 0.79 = Strong, 0.80 – 1.00 Very Strong

To address Research Question 2, the result in Table 2 shows a Pearson correlation coefficient ($r = 0.803$), indicating a very strong positive linear relationship between guided play and nursery pupils’ school attendance in Rivers State. This coefficient suggests that approximately 80% of the maximum possible positive relationship exists between the two variables, reflecting a very strong relationship. Therefore, there is a strong relationship between guided play and nursery pupils’ school attendance in Rivers State.

Research Question 3: *What is the relationship between structured play and nursery pupils' school attendance in Rivers State?*

Table 3: Pearson Product-Moment Correlation (PPMC) showing the Relationship between Structured Play and Nursery Pupils' School Attendance in Rivers State

Variables	n	df	r	Decision
Structured Play	364			
		362	0.811	Very Strong Relationship
Nursery Pupils' School Attendance	364			

Decision Rule: 0.00 – 0.19 = Very Weak, 0.20 – 0.39 = Weak, 0.40 – 0.59 = Moderate, 0.60 – 0.79 = Strong, 0.80 – 1.00 Very Strong

To address Research Question 3, the result in Table 3 shows a Pearson correlation coefficient ($r = 0.811$), indicating a very strong positive linear relationship between structured play and nursery pupils' school attendance in Rivers State. This coefficient suggests that approximately 81% of the maximum possible positive relationship exists between the two variables, reflecting a very strong relationship.

Thus, there is a strong relationship between structured play and nursery pupils' school attendance in Rivers State.

Test of Hypotheses

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant relationship between free play and nursery pupils' school attendance in Rivers State.

Table 4: Test of Hypothesis on the Relationship between Free Play and Nursery Pupils' School Attendance in Rivers State

Variables	n	df	r	p-value	alpha level	Decision
Free Play	364					
		362	0.872	0.000	0.05	Fail to Accept H_0 (Significant)
Nursery Pupils' School Attendance	364					

For Hypothesis 1, the result in Table 4 reveals a very strong positive linear relationship between free play and nursery pupils' school attendance ($r = 0.872$). However, this relationship is statistically significant at the 0.05 level, as the observed p-value ($p = 0.000$) does not exceed the specified alpha level of 0.05. Accordingly, the null hypothesis failed to be accepted, indicating that free play exerts a statistically significant relationship with nursery pupils' school attendance in Rivers State.

Hence, there is a significant relationship between free play and nursery pupils' school attendance in Rivers State.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant relationship between guided play and nursery pupils’ school attendance in Rivers State.

Table 5: Test of Hypothesis on the Relationship between Guided and Nursery Pupils’ School Attendance in Rivers State

Variables	n	df	r	p-value	alpha level	Decision
Guided Play	364					
		362	0.803	0.000	0.05	Fail to Accept Ho ₂ (Significant)
Nursery Pupils’ School Attendance	364					

For Hypothesis 2, the result in Table 5 reveals a very strong positive linear relationship between guided play and nursery pupils’ school attendance ($r = 0.803$). However, this relationship is statistically significant at the 0.05 level, as the observed p-value ($p = 0.000$) does not exceed the specified alpha level of 0.05. Accordingly, the null hypothesis failed to be accepted, indicating that guided play exerts a statistically significant relationship with nursery pupils’ school attendance in Rivers State.

Hence, there is a significant relationship between guided play and nursery pupils’ school attendance in Rivers State.

Hypothesis 3: There is no significant relationship between structured play and nursery pupils’ school attendance in Rivers State.

Table 6: Test of Hypothesis on the Relationship between Structured Play and Nursery Pupils’ School Attendance in Rivers State

Variables	n	df	r	p-value	alpha level	Decision
Structured Play	364					
		362	0.811	0.000	0.05	Fail to Accept Ho ₃ (Significant)
Nursery Pupils’ School Attendance	364					

For Hypothesis 3, the result in Table 6 reveals a very strong positive linear relationship between structured play and nursery pupils’ school attendance ($r = 0.811$). However, this relationship is statistically significant at the 0.05 level, as the observed p-value ($p = 0.000$) does not exceed the specified alpha level of 0.05. Accordingly, the null hypothesis failed to be accepted, indicating that structured play exerts a statistically significant relationship with nursery pupils’ school attendance in Rivers State.

Hence, there is a significant relationship between structured play and nursery pupils’ school attendance in Rivers State.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The first finding of the study revealed a very strong relationship between free play and nursery pupils’ school attendance in Rivers State. Also, a corresponding hypothesis tested established a significant relationship between free play and nursery pupils’ school attendance in Rivers State. These findings are in agreement with Wood (2014), Pyle and Danniels (2017), Zosh *et al.* (2018), Bodrova and Leong (2019), Cheruiyot (2024), and Obijiofor *et al.* (2024), whose studies affirmed that a very strong and significant relationship exists between free play and pupils’ school attendance. This finding is further explained by the fact that free play creates an enjoyable, child-centred learning environment that increases pupils’

motivation to attend school regularly and reduces absenteeism in nursery schools in Rivers State. This implies that integrating free play into nursery school programmes can be an effective strategy for improving pupils' regular school attendance and the early child education system in Rivers State.

The second finding of the study revealed a very strong relationship between guided play and nursery pupils' school attendance in Rivers State. Also, a corresponding hypothesis tested established a significant relationship between guided play and nursery pupils' school attendance in Rivers State. These findings are in line with Weisberg et al. (2016), Toub et al. (2018), Allee-Herndon et al. (2019), and Hassinger-Das et al. (2020), whose scholarly works averred that there is a very strong and significant link between guided play and pupils' school attendance. This finding may be further explained based on the fact that in my nursery schools in Rivers State, guided play combines structured learning with enjoyment, which helps pupils feel supported and engaged, and at the same time encourages consistent school attendance. This implies that the deliberate use of guided play by teachers can significantly enhance pupils' engagement and promote regular school attendance in nursery schools in Rivers State.

Lastly, the third finding of the study showed a very strong relationship between structured play and nursery pupils' school attendance in Rivers State. Also, a corresponding hypothesis tested established a significant relationship between structured play and nursery pupils' school attendance in Rivers State. These findings are in tandem with Saracho (2012), Bergen (2014), Ramani and Brownell (2014), Moyles (2015), and Hedges and Cooper (2018), whose scholarly evidences attest that structured play very strongly correlates with pupils' school attendance. A possible further explanation may be due to the fact that structured play provides routine, clear expectations, and purposeful activities that foster discipline and a sense of security, thereby encouraging pupils' regular attendance in nursery schools in Rivers State. This implies that incorporating structured play into daily nursery school routines can promote stability and discipline that support improved nursery pupils' school attendance in Rivers State.

CONCLUSION

The study concludes that play-based learning strategies, such as free play, guided play, and structured play, have a very strong and significant relationship with nursery pupils' school attendance in Rivers State, Nigeria. This indicates that effective integration of play-based learning in nursery education is crucial for enhancing pupils' regular school attendance and sustaining early childhood engagement.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings and conclusions of the study, the following are recommended:

1. Nursery school proprietors and teachers in Rivers State should continue to integrate daily free play periods into the curriculum to create enjoyable learning environments that motivate pupils to attend school regularly.
2. Teachers should always be trained and encouraged to use guided play strategies that balance structure with flexibility, as this approach supports pupils' engagement and sustains consistent school attendance in nursery schools across Rivers State.
3. Education stakeholders and school administrators should ensure the systematic use of structured play activities to provide routine, discipline, and emotional security, thereby strengthening pupils' regular attendance in nursery schools in Rivers State.

REFERENCES

- Allee-Herndon, K. A., Roberts, S. K., & Stevenson, A. (2019). Putting the "play" back in play-based learning: Teacher perceptions of play in kindergarten classrooms. *Early Childhood Education Journal*, 47(4), 437–446. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10643-019-00961-7>
- Bodrova, E., & Leong, D. J. (2019). *Tools of the mind: The Vygotskian approach to early childhood education* (3rd ed.). Pearson.
- Cheruiyot, B. (2024). *Effectiveness of play-based learning method in promotion of early literacy skills among ECDE children*. *East African Journal of Education Studies*. <https://doi.org/10.37284/eajes.7.3.2178>

- Fisher, K. R., Hirsh-Pasek, K., Golinkoff, R. M., Singer, D. G., & Berk, L. (2013). Playing around in school: Implications for learning and educational policy. *Oxford Review of Education*, 39(1), 25–42. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03054985.2012.760990>
- Hassinger-Das, B., Zosh, J. M., Hirsh-Pasek, K., Golinkoff, R. M., McDermott, C., & Pepler, K. (2020). Learning landscapes: Designing play-based environments to support learning. *Human Development*, 64(2), 87–106. <https://doi.org/10.1159/000506363>
- HealthyChildren. (2024, October 10). *School attendance, truancy & chronic absenteeism*. American Academy of Pediatrics. <https://www.healthychildren.org/English/ages-stages/gradeschool/school/Pages/School-Attendance-Truancy-Chronic-Absenteeism.aspx>
- Hirsh-Pasek, K., Zosh, J. M., Golinkoff, R. M., Gray, J. H., Robb, M. B., & Kaufman, J. (2020). Putting education in “educational” apps: Lessons from the science of learning. *Psychological Science in the Public Interest*, 21(1), 1–44. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1529100620924765>
- Kearney, C. A., & González, G. (2022). School attendance and school absenteeism: A primer for clinicians and educators. *Frontiers in Education*. <https://www.frontiersin.org/articles/10.3389/feduc.2022.1044608/full>
- Nicolopoulou, A. (2018). The power of play in education. *American Journal of Play*, 11(1), 1–6.
- Obijiofor, E. O., Ugwele, N. A., & Onyenwe, C. Y. (2024). Investigating the correlation between play-based learning and social skills development in nursery school children in Southeastern Nigeria. *International Journal of Research*, 6(4), 76-98.
- Parker, R., et al. (2022). Learning through play at school — a framework for policy and practice. *Frontiers in Education*, 7, Article 751801. <https://www.frontiersin.org/articles/10.3389/feduc.2022.751801/full>
- Parker, R., Thomsen, B. S., & Berry, A. (2022). Learning through play at school: A framework for policy and practice. *Frontiers in Education*, 7, 751801. <https://doi.org/10.3389/feduc.2022.751801>
- Pyle, A., & Danniels, E. (2017). A continuum of play-based learning: The role of the teacher in play-based pedagogy and the fear of hijacking play. *Early Education and Development*, 28(3), 274–289. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10409289.2016.1220771>
- Pyle, A., DeLuca, C., & Danniels, E. (2017). A scoping review of research on play-based pedagogies in kindergarten education. *Review of Education*, 5(3), 311–351. <https://doi.org/10.1002/rev3.3097>
- Toub, T. S., Rajan, V., Golinkoff, R. M., & Hirsh-Pasek, K. (2018). Guided play: A solution to the play versus learning dichotomy. *Evolutionary Perspectives on Child Development and Education*, 117–141. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-93734-4_8
- UNESCO Institute for Statistics. (n.d.). *Glossary — school participation and attendance indicators*. <https://databrowser.uis.unesco.org/resources/glossary/1952>
- UNESCO. (2023). *Nigeria: Education country brief*. International Institute for Capacity Building in Africa.
- UNESCO. (2025). *Why early childhood care and education matters*. <https://www.unesco.org/en/articles/why-early-childhood-care-and-education-matters> UNESCO
- UNICEF & LEGO Foundation. (2018). *Learning through play: Strengthening learning through play in early childhood education programmes*. <https://www.unicef.org/media/48446/file/Learning-through-play-brief-2018.pdf>
- UNICEF & LEGO Foundation. (2018). *Learning through play: Strengthening learning through play in early childhood education programmes*. UNICEF.
- UNICEF. (2025). *Education*. UNICEF Nigeria.
- Weisberg, D. S., Hirsh-Pasek, K., & Golinkoff, R. M. (2016). Guided play: Where curricular goals meet a playful pedagogy. *Mind, Brain, and Education*, 10(3), 142–152. <https://doi.org/10.1111/mbe.12110>
- Wood, E. (2014). The play-pedagogy interface in contemporary debates. *Early Years*, 34(2), 145–156. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09575146.2014.903241>
- Zosh, J. M., Hopkins, E. J., Jensen, H., Liu, C., Neale, D., Hirsh-Pasek, K., Solis, S. L., & Whitebread, D. (2018). *Learning through play: A review of the evidence*. LEGO Foundation.